

As per Ayurveda use of Trayodashyang Guggul and Manyabasti in the Management of Cervical Spondylosis – A Case Study

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Abstract

Ayurveda is an ancient system of medicine practicing from the ancient time and offers many holistic approaches for health management. In Ayurveda prevention and management of many diseases including treatment of *manyastambha* has suggested. In modern science *manyastambha* is called as cervical spondylosis. The signs and symptoms of *manyastambha* can be correlated with cervical spondylosis. In general term its affect the spinal discs due to age related wear and tear. As the disks dehydrate and shrink, signs of osteoarthritis develop including bony projections along the edges of bones [bone spurs]. Cervical spondylosis is very common and worsens with the age. More than 85% of people older than age of 50 years are affected by cervical spondylosis. Young generation is also facing the problem of cervical spondylosis due to over use of computers and mobiles, and other electronic gadgets. For most people, cervical spondylosis causes no symptoms, when symptoms do occur, non-surgical treatments often are effective. In present case study, a diagnosed case of cervical spondylosis, chief complaints were pain and stiffness over the neck since 8 months and pain over the neck was radiating towards the right arm. In treatment externally *manyabasti* and *patyra pottali swedan* was given and during this procedure, *ayurvedic* medicines mainly use of *trayodashyang guggul* also given. There is a complete relief in the parameters like neck and stiffness whereas the parameters like pain in arm and vertigo has also shown significant improvement.

Keywords: Ayurveda, *Manyastambha*, *Manyabasti*, Cervical spondylosis.

Introduction

Cervical spondylosis is a natural age related disease process that is associated with degenerative changes within the intervertebral disc. It is most commonly present as neck pain, which remain as one of the leading causes of disability and rising healthcare casts. This activity reviews the evaluation and management of cervical spondylosis and highlights the role of inter professional team in evaluating and treating patients with this condition.

Vata produces 80 types of *nanatmaj vyadhi* in body. *Manyastambha* has been included in 80 disorders of *vata*. *Manyastambha* is the clinical entity in which the back of the neck become stiff and rigid, movements of the neck impaired with pain. It can be correlated with cervical spondylosis in modern medicine.

Anatomical structure of Cervical Vertebrae.

Aim and Objectives

To assess the role of *Manyabasti* in *Manyastambha* (cervical spondylosis)

Material and Methods

- Study design: single arm clinical study.
- For ethical consideration consent has been taken from the patient before commencement of treatment.
- For the present study 38 yrs. old female patient having symptoms of *manyastambha* for 45 days is been discussed in detail manner.
- Patients were treated with *Sthanik Manyabasti*.

Case report

A 38 yrs. old female patient came to OPD with the complaints of pain in the neck and stiffness since 45 days tingling sensation and numbness in arm, pain radiating towards right arm since 45 days. Difficulty in neck movements.

- **Family History** – not significant.
- **Past History**- no relevant past history.
- **Surgical history**- no surgical history.
- Patient denied any history of trauma.
- **Tenderness**- +++ over cervical region.

Investigations

- **HB** – 12.5
- **TLC** – 7460
- **PT/INR**- 14.3/0.87
- **BSL** – 97

- **Urine analysis** – within normal limits

- **X-Ray report** – in cervical X- Ray degenerative changes and osteophytes were developed in cervical vertebrae.
- Other investigations were within normal limit.

X- Ray Image.

Pathophysiology of *Manya Basti*

Due to indulgence in the un wholesome food and activities leads to vitiating of *vata* and *vyana vayu*. The vitiating *vata* gets lodged in neck region resulting muscular pain in neck area.

Diagnosis – *Manyasthamba*.

Treatment Protocol

Following the *panchakarma* treatment namely *stanik basti* called *manyabasti*. In the morning for consecutive 14 day. The patient made to lie face down on the table. A circular ring was made the wheat flour of height 3 to 5 cm. the pre warmed *bala asahwagandha* oil was poured in the ring and filled to depth of about 3 centimeter. The temperature was maintained uniform throughout the procedure. The process was carried out for 30 minutes.

For *swedan*, use of *patra pottali sweda* is used it is highly effective in pain. Here small six chopped leaves of *nirgundi*, *errand*, along with lemon juice, *saindhav lavana* are fried in the pan using *nirgundi oil*. This fried content is tied in cotton cloth of around 12 inches length and made into a *pottali*.

This process should be done for at least 15 to 20 minutes. The procedure done for 14 days.

Images of *Manyabasti*

Internal medicine

Medicine	Dose	Anupan	Duration
<i>Trayodashyang Guggula</i>	2 Tab BD	Lukewarm water	14 Day
Tab. <i>Shallaki</i>	1 TDS	Lukewarm water	14 Day

Discussion

The results were assessed on basis of symptomatic improvement using VAS. Cervical spondylosis emerging as a widespread problem in the society due to the overuses of computer technologies. Lack of exercise and incorrect posture. *Manyabasti* is a procedure where *bahyasnehana* and *swedan* done. Due to warm oil cervical region blood supply of that part is increased and inflammation is reduced. *Bala* and *ashwagandha* both are *balya* and *bruhana* and *vatshamak*. It nourishes the intervertebral disc. *Nirgundi* and *errand patra* has *vatshamak* and *shotshara*. Due to this property pain and inflammation is reduced. *Trayodashyang guggula* reduced the pain and inflammation. The main ingredient of *Trayodashyang guggula* is *sudhdha guggulu*, which is the best *vathara*. *Shallaki* as it has *ushna virya*, *tikshna guna* it acts as *vata shamak*.

Shallaki also increase *dhatvagni* by its *tikta rasa*, leading proper nutrition of *dhatu*s, whereas improvement of the symptoms of *vata kshayta* is due to *rasayan* (immunomodulation) and *brihamniya prabhava* of *shallaki*.

Conclusion

Cervical spondylosis is one of the commonest degenerative neurological condition by which the major population has been affected. The *panchakarma* involving all the three aspect of preventive, nutritive and curative treatment is all in one methodology. Cervical spondylosis can be best managed in relieving signs and symptoms and providing the best comfort by judiciously adopting various *panchakarma* procedure at regular intervals based on *avastha* of the diseases and patients. *Panchakarma* have been proved useful for cervical spondylosis in alleviating symptoms and to reduce disability.

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